

SOME EXPRESSIONS OF THE SMARANDACHE PRIME FUNCTION

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Abstract The main purpose of this paper is using elementary arithmetical functions to give some expressions of the Smarandache Prime Function $P(n)$.

In this article we gave some expressions of the Smarandache Prime Function $P(n)$ (see reference [1]), using elementary arithmetical functions. The Smarandache Prime Function is the complementary of the Prime Characteristic Function:

$$P(n) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } n \text{ is a prime,} \\ 1 & \text{if } n \text{ is a composite.} \end{cases}$$

Expression 1.

$$P(n) = 1 - \left\lfloor \frac{lcm(1, 2, \dots, n)}{n \cdot lcm(1, 2, \dots, n-1)} \right\rfloor,$$

where $\lfloor \cdot \rfloor$ is the floor function (see reference [2]).

Proof. We consider three cases:

Case 1: If $n = p$ with p prime, then we have

$$lcm(1, 2, \dots, p) = lcm(lcm(1, 2, \dots, p-1), p) = p \cdot lcm(1, 2, \dots, p-1)$$

Therefore we have: $P(n) = 0$.

Case 2: If $n = p^\alpha$ with p is prime and α is a positive integer greater than one, we may have

$$\begin{aligned} & \left\lfloor \frac{lcm(1, 2, \dots, n)}{n \cdot lcm(1, 2, \dots, n-1)} \right\rfloor \\ &= \left\lfloor \frac{lcm(1, 2, \dots, p^\alpha)}{n \cdot lcm(1, 2, \dots, p^\alpha - 1)} \right\rfloor \\ &= \left\lfloor \frac{lcm(lcm(1, 2, \dots, p^{\alpha-1}), \dots, p^\alpha - 1), p^\alpha}{n \cdot lcm(1, 2, \dots, p^\alpha - 1)} \right\rfloor \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \left\lfloor \frac{p \cdot \text{lcm}(1, 2, \dots, p^{\alpha-1}, \dots, p^{\alpha} - 1)}{n \cdot (1, 2, \dots, p^{\alpha} - 1)} \right\rfloor \\
&= \left\lfloor \frac{p}{n} \right\rfloor = 0.
\end{aligned}$$

So we have: $P(n) = 1$.

Case 3: If $n = a \cdot b$ with $\text{gcd}(a, b) = 1$ and $a, b > 1$. We can suppose $a < b$, then we have

$$\begin{aligned}
&\text{lcm}(1, 2, \dots, a, \dots, b, \dots, n) \\
&= \text{lcm}(1, 2, \dots, a, \dots, b, \dots, n-1, a \cdot b) \\
&= \text{lcm}(1, 2, \dots, a, \dots, b, \dots, n-1)
\end{aligned}$$

and therefore we have:

$$\begin{aligned}
P(n) &= 1 - \left\lfloor \frac{\text{lcm}(1, 2, \dots, n)}{n \cdot \text{lcm}(1, 2, \dots, n-1)} \right\rfloor \\
&= 1 - \left\lfloor \frac{1}{n} \right\rfloor = 1 - 0 = 1
\end{aligned}$$

With this the expression one is proven.

Expression 2. [3],[4]

$$P(n) = - \left\lfloor \frac{2 - \sum_{i=1}^n \left\lfloor \frac{n}{i} \right\rfloor - \left\lfloor \frac{n-1}{i} \right\rfloor}{n} \right\rfloor$$

Proof. We consider $d(n) = \sum_{i=1}^n \left\lfloor \frac{n}{i} \right\rfloor - \left\lfloor \frac{n-1}{i} \right\rfloor$ is the number of divisors of n because:

$$\left\lfloor \frac{n}{i} \right\rfloor - \left\lfloor \frac{n-1}{i} \right\rfloor = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } i \text{ divides } n, \\ 0 & \text{if } i \text{ not divide } n. \end{cases}$$

If $n = p$ prime we have $d(n) = 2$ and therefore $P(n) = 0$.

If n is composite we have $d(n) > 2$ and therefore:

$$-1 < \frac{2 - d(n)}{n} < 0 \implies P(n) = 1.$$

Expression 3.

We can also prove the following expression:

$$P(n) = 1 - \left\lfloor \frac{1}{n} \cdot \text{GCD} \left(\binom{n}{1}, \binom{n}{2}, \dots, \binom{n}{n-1} \right) \right\rfloor,$$

where $\binom{n}{i}$ is the binomial coefficient.

Can the reader prove this last expression?

References

- [1] E. Burton, Smarandache Prime and Coprime Functions, <http://www.gallup.unm.edu/~smarandache/primfnct.txt>.
- [2] S. M. Ruiz, A New Formula for the n -th Prime, *Smarandache Notions Journal* **15** 2005.
- [3] S. M. Ruiz, A Functional Recurrence to Obtain the Prime Numbers Using the Smarandache Prime Function, *Smarandache Notions Journal* **11** (2000), 56.
- [4] S. M. Ruiz, The General Term of the Prime Number Sequence and the Smarandache Prime Function, *Smarandache Notions Journal*, **11** (2000), 59.